

2024 ANNUAL REPORT

**ADVANCING EXCELLENCE,
REALISING IMPACT**

**SCIENCE
EUROPE**
Shaping the future of research

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PREFACE

Science is a driving force for progress, but only when it is guided by shared values, open collaboration, and a commitment to serve society. In 2024, Science Europe worked to ensure that research systems across Europe not only respond to global challenges – but lead with purpose, integrity, and ambition.

MARI SUNDLI TVEIT / PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE

FOREWORD

2024 was a year of continued progress and renewed purpose for Science Europe. In a rapidly evolving global landscape, the importance of strong, inclusive, and values-driven research systems has never been more evident.

Amid global uncertainties, the ongoing climate crisis, and rapid technological change shaping our societies, research remains a vital pillar that drives progress and addresses the critical challenges we face.

I am honoured to have performed my first year as President of Science Europe – a role that has deepened my commitment to furthering the shared goals of our community and championing the transformative power of research.

Science Europe advanced its mission to strengthen the European Research Area and elevate the role of science in addressing societal challenges. We championed values-driven reform in areas such as research assessment, careers, integrity, and open science – ensuring that researchers are supported by inclusive, fair, and sustainable research systems. Through our continued work on research culture, we underlined the importance of creating environments that foster excellence, trust, and collaboration.

In 2024, we also took important steps to support the greening of research practices and the responsible use of artificial intelligence in science. We launched new frameworks and guidance to equip our member organisations to lead change – not just through what research they fund and perform, but also how they do so. Our work reinforced the principle that research systems must model the values we wish to see in society.

Science Europe's voice resonated strongly in shaping European policy, from contributing to the development of the next EU Framework Programme to co-leading actions under the ERA Policy Agenda.

Our unwavering support to the National Research Foundation of Ukraine, and our engagement in international platforms, through partnerships with Africa, Ukraine, China, and our work with the Global Research Council, reflected our commitment to global co-operation based on equity, reciprocity, and trust.

None of this would be possible without the dedication and expertise of our Member Organisations and our dedicated staff. I am deeply grateful to them for their continued engagement, insights, and shared ambition. Their commitment to excellence, shared values, and the free exchange of ideas has driven meaningful progress in an increasingly interconnected and uncertain world.

Together, we are building research ecosystems that are open, ethical, inclusive, and equipped to meet the defining challenges of our time.

As we look ahead to 2025, Science Europe will continue to serve as a platform for collaboration, advocacy, and action. With science at the heart of Europe's future, we will remain steadfast in promoting research policies that advance knowledge, strengthen society, and leave no one behind.

"Becoming President of Science Europe has been both an honour and a responsibility. At a time when the role of research in society is more critical than ever, I am proud to lead a community that champions excellence, inclusivity, and collaboration.

Together, we shape research systems that not only advance knowledge but also embody the values we need to build a more resilient and equitable world."

**MARI SUNDLI TVEIT /
PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE**

2024 TOP ACHIEVEMENTS

Continuing Support for the National Research Foundation of Ukraine

Science Europe reaffirmed its **steadfast support** for National Research Foundation of Ukraine; promoting its integration into the European Research Area and the development of open science practices; supporting our members' efforts to strengthen Ukrainian research systems through funding and equipment; and championing the resilience of the Ukrainian research community.

Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments

Development of a broader understanding of the meaning of diversity for research funding and performing organisations, and recommendations such as the monitoring of processes for forms of potential bias or the allocation of dedicated budgets to implement diversity-related policies and practices, to develop more inclusive research cultures.

High Level Conference on Science Communication under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU, and the publication of Strategic Conclusions

Advancement of science communication as a strategic priority of Science Europe, co-organising a high-level **conference** together with FRNS and FWO, and the publication of **key recommendations** to embed science communication strategically from the outset of research programmes and projects, based on a set of core principles, to promote scientific literacy and public trust in science.

Vote for Science Campaign for the European Parliament elections

The launch of the **Vote for Science campaign** for the European Parliament elections, calling on candidates to support five key pledges that highlight the essential role of science in tackling societal challenges: namely, invest in science for society, culture and competitiveness; ensure freedom of scientific enquiry; promote collaboration, openness and equity; advance equality, diversity and inclusion; and integrate science communication from the outset in research programmes.

Guidance on Science for Policy Activities

Publication of new **Guidance on Science for Policy Activities**, empowering research funding and performing organisations to strengthen their role in science-informed policymaking, identifying key principles such as the need for institutional mandates, dedicated resources and multi-disciplinary approaches and suggesting practical actions based on the values of quality, integrity and transparency.

10 Key Messages for the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10)

Development of **strong advocacy messages** on the need for an independent, inclusive and sustainable framework programme for research and innovation, which protects academic freedom, promotes international collaboration and balances investment between low and high technology readiness levels (TRLs).

Framework for the Environmental Sustainability of Research Organisations

Collaborating with Science Europe Member Organisations to define eight strategic objectives to improve the environmental sustainability of research, including sustainable travel, responsible digitalisation, and integrating environmental criteria into research practices.

Survey Report Strategic Approaches to, and Research Assessment of, Open Science

Achieving greater understanding of how Science Europe Member Organisations are approaching open science as a strategic priority, its incorporation into the reform of research assessment practices, and facilitating mutual learning and promoting policy alignment between members.

2024 TOP ACHIEVEMENTS

Coordinating Science Europe Member Organisations in setting up Open Research Europe

Participated actively in a process to set up a consortium supported by the European Commission to establish the new Open Research Europe (ORE), a repository of scientific publications free for authors and for readers, facilitating the involvement of research performing organisations. To date, 11 Science Europe Member Organisations have signed a statement expressing their intent to take part.

2024 High Level Workshop on the European Research Area 'Strengthening European cohesion and competitiveness through research and innovation: the science agenda for European progress in a global context'

Co-organised with HUN-REN and MTA under the auspices of the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU.

Development of a **shared agenda** on measures to enhance Europe's global R&I competitiveness, including freedom of scientific enquiry, improved conditions for researcher mobility, increased investment at national and European level to strengthen Europe's research and innovation ecosystem. Collaborative research partnerships based on equitable access to scientific knowledge and reciprocity are crucial to tackle the global challenges we face.

Identification of measures to improve research collaboration between Europe and Africa, as part of a series of workshops with other world regions

Identification of specific actions to develop more equitable research partnerships with African research organisations, including co-designed funding models, improved researcher mobility, and greater recognition of African priorities in international partnerships, at the first in a series of annual workshops between Science Europe Member organisations and other world regions.

Reciprocity in Multilateral Research Collaboration as part of the Science Summit during the 79th UN General Assembly

Promotion of the need for equitable, inclusive and trust-based research partnerships to tackle pressing societal challenges, which prioritise academic freedom, equitable access to knowledge and infrastructure and recognition of indigenous knowledge systems.

2024 AT A GLANCE: PUBLICATIONS

Q1

JANUARY

19 January: Publication of Joint Statement Investing More in RD&I as a Strategic Move for Europe's Future Prosperity

31 January: Publication of Open Letter European Research and Higher Education Organisations Call On Commission Not to Neglect Their Needs in Lawmaking

FEBRUARY

1 February: Publication of Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments

8 February: Publication of Response to EU Call for Evidence on Implementation of the GDPR

MARCH

25 March: Publication of Science Communication Conference Strategic Conclusions

Q2

APRIL

4 April: Publication of Guidance on Science for Policy Activities

25 April: Publication of Science Europe Action Plan supporting the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

26 April: Publication of Briefing on the ERA Policy Agenda

26 April: Internal Survey on 'The Uses of Artificial Intelligence in Research Processes: Analysis of Outcomes and Ways Forward'

MAY

2 May: Publication of Initial Position in response to European Commission Consultation on the White Paper on R&D on Dual-Use Technologies

JUNE

4 June: Publication of Research Matters Open Letter: A call to strengthen research and innovation in Europe

5 June: Publication of updated Science Europe Multi-annual Action Plan 2021–2026

Q3

JULY

5 July: Publication of 10 Key Messages for the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10)

11 July: Publication of Position Statement Integrity at the Heart of Healthy and Effective Research Cultures

SEPTEMBER

10 September: Publication of Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software: Recommendations for RFOs and RPOs

30 September: Publication of Response to European Commission Consultation on the NEW ERA: Four Years On

Q4

OCTOBER

3 October: Publication of Joint Statement on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

23 October: Publication of Survey Report Strategic Approaches to, and Research Assessment of, Open Science

NOVEMBER

14 November: Publication of Framework for the Environmental Sustainability of Research Organisations

20 November: Publication of Position Statement 'What European Research Needs'

28 November: Publication of Response to global consultation on the UNESCO Draft Principles on Open Science Monitoring

DECEMBER

4 December: Publication of Concluding Statement on Commitment to Strengthening European R&I, following the 2024 High Level Workshop on the ERA

12 December: Publication of Survey Report on Appraising Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Research Organisations

12 December: Publication of Discussion Paper on Artificial Intelligence

19 December: Publication of Report of the 2024 High Level Workshop on the ERA

20 December: Publication of Event report Attractive Careers in Research: the Expectations & Roles of Different Stakeholder Groups

2024 AT A GLANCE: EVENTS

Q1

FEBRUARY

1 February: Launch event for [Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments](#) (Brussels, Belgium)

11 February: Launch of Women in Science campaign between International Day of Women and Girls in Science and International Women's Day (*online*)

15 February: Internal workshop on Artificial Intelligence in Research Evaluation (*online*)

MARCH

12-13 March: [Unlocking the Power of Science Communication in Policy Making](#). High Level Conference on Science Communication, co-organised with FNRS, FWO and ETAG, under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU (Brussels, Belgium)

Q2

APRIL

4 April: Launch Event [Guidance on Science for Policy Activities](#) Hosted by FWO (Brussels, Belgium)

MAY

15 May: Internal Workshop on Voting for Science: the role of science in Europe Hosted by FWO (Brussels, Belgium)

17 May: Launch of [Vote for Science Campaign for the European Parliament elections](#)

21 May-4 June: Series of three webinars on [Greening Research](#) organised in co-operation with ANR, DFG, AKA, FORMAS, FCT, INFN, NWO, SNSF, and UKRI (*online*)

JUNE

28 June: Internal Workshop on Trends in Implementing AI in Research Organisations and the Legal Aspects

Q3

SEPTEMBER

17 September: Round Table on [Reciprocity in Multilateral Research Collaboration](#) as part of the Science Summit during the 79th UN General Assembly, co-organised with RCN (New York, United States of America)

Q4

OCTOBER

28-31 October: 2024 GRC European Regional Meeting co-organised with ETAG (Tallinn, Estonia)

30 October: [Workshop on Cooperation between Africa and Europe – best practice, future possibilities, and the role of Science Europe](#). Co-organised with ETAG (Tallinn, Estonia)

NOVEMBER

4-5 November: [Workshop on Attractive Careers in Research: the Expectations & Roles of Different Stakeholder Groups](#) (Brussels, Belgium)

8 November: Internal Webinar on Environmental Sustainability of Research and Research-related activities (*online*)

11 November: Science Europe admitted as Official Observer to the UNFCCC

14 November: [Conference on Rethinking Research Assessment](#), organised by the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI), together with Science Europe and other partners (Bucharest, Romania)

19-20 November: 2024 High Level [Workshop on the European Research Area 'Strengthening European cohesion and competitiveness through research and innovation: the science agenda for European progress in a global context](#). 'Co-organised with HUN-REN and MTA under the auspices of the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU (Budapest, Hungary)

29 November: Internal Workshop: Artificial Intelligence and Science Communication (*online*)

DECEMBER

4 December: Internal Workshop on Monitoring Cross-Border Collaboration (*online*)

8-14 December: 2nd [Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) (Cape Town, South Africa)

Thanks to Science Europe Member Organisations for their continuing support and active participation in our activities during 2024

MEET THE SCIENCE EUROPE MEMBERS

1 FWF Österreichischer Wissenschaftsfonds	2 ÖAW ÖSTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	3 fnrs LA LIBERTÉ DE CHERCHER	4 fwo
5 HRZZ Croatian Science Foundation	6 GAČR CZECH SCIENCE FOUNDATION	7 INDEPENDENT RESEARCH FUND DENMARK	8 Danmarks Grundforskningsfond Danish National Research Foundation
9 Estonian Research Council	10 Research Council of Finland	11 anr [®] agence nationale de la recherche	12 DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft German Research Foundation
13	14 HUN-REN Hungarian Research Network	15 MTA HUNGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	16 rannis
17 HRB Health Research Board	18 Taighde Éireann Research Ireland	19 INFN Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare	20 Latvian Council of Science
21 Lietuvos mokslo taryba	22 ENR	23 NWC	24 Research Council of Norway
25 FNP Foundation for Polish Science	26 NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE POLAND	27 fct Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	28 uefiscdi
29 Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia	30 SLOVAK RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	31 aris (Austrian Research and Innovation Agency)	32
33 CSIC CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS	34 ISC Instituto de Salud Carlos III	35 FORTE! Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare	36 FORMAS
37 Vetenskapsrådet	38 Swiss National Science Foundation	39 NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION OF UKRAINE	40 UK Research and Innovation

2024 IN NUMBERS

MEMBERSHIP

40

MEMBER ORGANISATIONS

30

EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

CONTRIBUTING (APPROX.)

25.1
bn €

TO RESEARCH PER YEAR

SOCIAL MEDIA

15K

FOLLOWERS

21K

IMPRESSIONS

10K

FOLLOWERS

EVENTS

10

ONSITE EVENTS ORGANISED BY SCIENCE EUROPE

106

EXTERNAL EVENTS WITH CONTRIBUTIONS BY SCIENCE EUROPE

22

MEETINGS OF SCIENCE EUROPE GOVERNANCE AND WORKING GROUPS

PUBLICATIONS

34

POLICY POSITIONS, GUIDELINES & REPORTS

47

HIGH-LEVEL PRESS MENTIONS

VIDEO PRODUCTIONS

5

WEBSITE

37K

WEBSITE VISITORS

108K

WEBSITE PAGE VIEWS

NEWSLETTERS

11

MEMBER NEWSLETTERS

2

PUBLIC NEWSLETTERS

[Science Europe updates August 2024](#)

[Science Europe updates January 2025](#)

Women in Science 2024

- [Interview with Mari Sundli Tveit](#)
- [Interview with Katarina Bjelke](#)
- [Interview with Milica Đurić-Jovičić](#)
- [Interview with Anna Di Caccio](#)

[Wrap-up of the 2024 High Level Workshop on the ERA](#)

GOVERNING BOARD ELECTED NOVEMBER 2023

PRESIDENT

Mari Sundli Tveit
Chief Executive of
the Research Council
of Norway
(RCN)
Norway

VICE PRESIDENTS

Marcel Levi
President of the
Dutch Research
Council
(NWO),
*Vice-President
representing RFOs*
Netherlands

**Francisco Javier
Moreno Fuentes**
Vice-President for International
Affairs, Spanish National
Research Council (CSIC),
*Vice-President
representing RPOs*
Spain

BOARD MEMBERS

Katarina Bjelke
Director General
of the Swedish
Research Council
(VR)
Sweden

Adrian Curaj
Director General
of the Executive
Agency for Higher
Education, Research,
Development and
Innovation Funding
of Romania
(UEFISCDI)
Romania

Anna Di Ciaccio
Director of the
National Institute for
Nuclear Physics
(INFN)
Italy

**Milica Đurić-
Jovičić**
(until 30 July 2024)
Acting Director
of the Science Fund
of the Republic of
Serbia
(SFRS)
Serbia

Christof Gattringer
President of the
Austrian Science
Fund
(FWF)
Austria

Matthias Koenig
Vice-President of the
German Research
Foundation
(DFG)
Germany

Anu Noorma
(from 8 Nov 2024)
Director General
of the Estonian
Research Council
(ETAG)
Estonia

Christopher Smith
Executive Chair of
the Arts and
Humanities Research
Council, UK Research
and Innovation
(UKRI)
United Kingdom

VISION AND MISSION

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking scientific research in Europe. It brings together the expertise of some of the largest and best-known research organisations in the world to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society.

VISION

Science Europe’s vision is for a European Research Area with optimal conditions to support robust education, research, and innovation systems. This is a European Research Area where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

MISSION

Science Europe’s mission is to define long-term perspectives for European research and to champion best-practice approaches, ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of humanity and the planet.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021–2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021–2026](#)

(Updated June 2024)

STRATEGY PLAN

The Strategy Plan has three strategic priorities that encapsulate Science Europe’s vision:

- Shape European research policy developments
- Contribute to the evolution of research culture
- Strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges

SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN PRIORITIES AND TOPICS

The Multiannual Action Plan was updated in June 2024 to reflect emerging priorities such as the use of Artificial Intelligence in research processes and the impact of research activities on the environment.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021–2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021–2026](#)
(Updated June 2024)

WORKING GROUPS IN 2024

- High-level Policy Network on the ERA and Cross-border Collaboration
- Working Group on Communication
- Working Group on Horizon Europe
- Working Group on Open Science
- Working Group on Research Culture
- Working Group on the Green and Digital Transition

An overview of the members of the Working Groups is provided in the [Annex](#)

SUPPORT FOR UKRAINE

In 2024, the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU) remained steadfast in advancing the country's research and innovation agenda, despite the severe challenges posed by the ongoing war.

Science Europe continued to prioritise its support for the NRFU, and its focus on open science and the upcoming Framework Programme. Moreover, Member Organisations supported NRFU through funding and equipment and organising trainings and study visits to enhance capacity

On 4 July 2024, Science Europe proudly joined in celebrating the sixth anniversary of the National Research Foundation of Ukraine. In just six years, the NRFU has enabled hundreds of research teams to access funding and equipment, even as the war has devastated infrastructure and displaced scientists. The foundation's continued leadership and independence underscore its commitment to integrating Ukraine into the global scientific community.

Science Europe supported the engagement of NRFU with other Science Europe members to boost its participation in Horizon Europe, following its accession to the programme in 2022 and the opening of the Horizon Europe office in Kyiv in October 2023, as well as its integration into the global research area. NRFU has also participated in a project to identify specific national challenges and opportunities regarding current measures on EU policies to improve R&I integration, and to identify structural obstacles to close the R&I divide across Europe.

The Science Europe Secretary General continues to serve as a member of the NRFU Board of International Councillors, providing support to policy development and strengthening the connections between NRFU and the policy stakeholders in the European research area, as well as with the European Commission. NRFU has also received support to develop its open science policies, and to contribute to initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Open Research Europe (ORE), and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

Beyond these activities, Science Europe members are also providing concrete support. Our dedicated webpage continues to document and share updates on initiatives to support the Ukrainian research community. These partnerships stand as a testament to the resilience of science in times of crisis, and to the shared European values of openness, collaboration, and solidarity.

Visit the Science Europe website to find out how our members are supporting the research community in Ukraine.

[+ scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/ukraine/](https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/ukraine/)

ACTIVITY AREAS

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH CULTURE

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Development of strategic frameworks and action plans to drive systemic change, embedding values-driven policies across research ecosystems.

Shaping collective understanding and actions on major research policy challenges through a series of high-impact events.

Promoting measures to ensure equality, inclusivity and diversity in research policy.

RESEARCH CULTURE

In 2024, Science Europe solidified its position as a leading voice in shaping research cultures, advancing its strategic work to foster more coherent, inclusive, and effective conditions for researchers and research ideas.

Through cross-cutting initiatives that connected open science, research assessment, integrity, and careers, the organisation worked to align policies and practices that support lasting cultural change.

2024 marked the third year of Science Europe's strategic focus on research culture. The organisation has established itself as a key voice in this field, promoting a holistic understanding of research cultures that spans open science, research assessment, research integrity, and careers in research.

A core objective this year was to build a common focal point across these policy areas. This means ensuring that initiatives in one domain - such as open science - do not inadvertently create challenges in another, such as research careers or research assessment. By fostering cross-cutting alignment, Science Europe supports policies and practices that drive positive cultural change and promote behaviours that improve research quality and impact.

The Working Group on Research Culture played a central role in delivering this strategic priority. It met four times in 2024 to define how Member Organisations understand and support research culture. It developed a framework for research cultures, building on Science Europe's 2022 Values Framework, and drafted a shared vision and long-term action plan.

The Vision and Framework were published in March 2025. They consolidate outputs from Science Europe's work since 2021, highlighting good practices, remaining barriers, and future opportunities. It also maps how different

research policy topics interconnect, ensuring coherent and mutually supportive actions across domains.

Several other key publications in 2024 also contributed to supporting the evolution of research cultures. In January, the [Practical Guide to Support Diversity in Research Environments](#) reflected on the challenges that research organisations face whilst trying to foster fair and inclusive research cultures. April saw the publication of the [Action Plan](#) to support activities to promote research assessment as part of Science Europe's participation in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). In July, a [Position Statement on Research Integrity](#) was launched, highlighting the role of integrity in fostering healthy and effective research environments. This was followed in October by the publication of the [Survey Report on Open Science and its Assessment](#), and in November, a workshop on [Careers in Research](#) explored the common and different expectations for careers in research by various stakeholder groups.

Looking ahead to 2025, the Vision and Framework for Research Cultures will provide a strategic roadmap for Member Organisations to continue advancing this agenda, so that, research culture remains central to policy development, supporting inclusive, high-quality, and impactful research.

+ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-culture>

“Strengthening research culture is not about isolated reforms - it is about creating a coherent and supportive system where open science, integrity, assessment, and careers work together to elevate the quality and impact of research. In 2024, we took significant steps toward that goal, and our upcoming Vision and Framework will provide the roadmap to guide continued progress across the European research ecosystem.”

MATTHIAS KOENIG / VICE-PRESIDENT OF THE GERMAN RESEARCH FOUNDATION (DFG)

RESEARCH CAREERS

In 2024, Science Europe advanced its work on improving research careers - an essential element of research culture - through a dedicated Careers in Research Workshop, held on 4 November.

Over 240 participants from 35 countries joined discussions on how to make research careers more attractive and sustainable. The event, developed by the Task Force on Research Careers, explored the expectations of researchers, employers, and policy makers. Key issues included job insecurity, limited

career pathways, and under-recognised skills. Participants emphasised the need for supportive conditions, flexible and diverse career paths, and a co-ordinated approach to career development across the research sector.

The workshop also addressed the links between research careers and broader policy areas such as open science, research assessment, and EDI. A follow-up meeting on 5 November for Science Europe Member Organisations discussed the outcomes from the workshop and identified actionable priorities, including setting minimum standards, developing career development plans, and protecting time for personal growth. A report was published in December 2024, and the Task Force will build on the outcomes to develop concrete recommendations in 2025.

REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

In 2024, Science Europe played a pivotal role in advancing research assessment reform through its active involvement in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), promoting transparency, inclusivity and responsible research evaluation practices.

Looking ahead, the organisation will continue to drive global efforts to reshape research assessment, ensuring systems are inclusive, diverse, and impactful.

As part of its ongoing commitment to reform research assessment, Science Europe played an active and strategic role in CoARA throughout the year. The coalition continues to be a key platform for promoting transparency, inclusivity, and responsible use of metrics in research evaluation systems. Virtually all Science Europe Member Organisations are engaged in at least one of the CoARA Expert Groups.

Until December, Secretary General Lidia Borrell-Damián represented Science Europe on the CoARA Steering Board. During her two-year term, she contributed to shaping the Coalition's governance, defining assessment criteria for National Chapters and Working Groups, and strengthening international collaboration with initiatives such as the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#), the [Latin American Forum on Research Assessment \(FOLEC\)](#), and within the [Global Research Council \(GRC\)](#).

Through its involvement in the [CoARA Boost](#) project, Science Europe led a work package dedicated to expanding global engagement, fostering new community participation, and building synergies with other international initiatives.

Collaboration with CoARA Working Groups remained a key priority. A joint Task Force on Open Science and Research Assessment - featuring representatives from Science Europe's Working Groups on Research Culture and Open Science - conducted a survey across Member Organisations to explore strategies for integrating open science

into assessment practices. With a 90% response rate, the survey's findings were published in October and discussed during a joint workshop that contributed to shared understanding and best practices.

To support Member Organisations in implementing the CoARA commitments, several forums and webinars were convened. The third CoARA Forum webinar, held on 23 January, provided updates on Working Groups and National Chapters, introduced the CoARA Boost project, and guided Member Organisations in drafting their one-year Action Plans. Science Europe's own Action Plan - detailing its reform priorities and alignment with broader initiatives - was published in March.

The first National Chapters Exchange Forum was held on 22-23 February in Porto, Portugal and organised by Science Europe, the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), INESC-TEC, and the University of Minho. The event brought together representatives from fifteen National Chapters to explore their role in addressing local challenges, developing outreach strategies, encouraging multilingual engagement, and evaluating impact. The approval of new Chapters in Portugal, Sweden, and the United Kingdom signalled continued momentum and growth.

In May, participation in the UN STI Forum underscored ongoing global engagement. Advocacy for the integration of open science principles in research assessment, emphasising the importance of open access publications and data transparency, was one of the recommendations resulting from the session.

At the Euroscience Open Forum (ESOF) in June, Science Europe hosted a dedicated session on CoARA Commitment #2, which calls for qualitative evaluation as core approach, supported by

responsible use of metrics. Contributions from the OPUS project and the Science Europe members Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN) highlighted evolving practices in this area. The discussions reinforced the importance of combining both qualitative and quantitative methods for robust, fair, and effective research assessment. Finally, in November, the Science Europe member Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI) hosted the international conference 'Rethinking Research Assessment', in Bucharest. Co-organised with Science Europe, the OPUS Project, CoARA, and the UNESCO Chair on Science and Innovation Policies (SNSPA), the event brought together key stakeholders to explore current practices, challenges, and innovations in research assessment and open science. The programme focused on three main themes: policies, researcher perspectives, and practical use cases, highlighting the essential role of research funding and performing organisations in driving meaningful reform and improving research quality and impact.

During 2025, Science Europe will continue to collaborate with the new CoARA Board elected in December 2024. It will focus on sustaining the momentum for reform of research assessment and the development of a broad membership base for the movement. This will ensure that reform efforts are inclusive, diverse, and reflect varied research ecosystems around the world.

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-assessment/>

"Reforming research assessment is essential to building more inclusive, transparent, and effective research systems. In 2024, Science Europe deepened its commitment to this transformation - working closely with partners across Europe and beyond to align practices, share knowledge, and empower our Member Organisations to lead meaningful change."

ADRIAN CURAJ / DIRECTOR GENERAL OF THE EXECUTIVE AGENCY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION FUNDING OF ROMANIA (UEFISCDI)

29 November 2024
Organisation of event:
RESEARCH-ON-RESEARCH
Bern, Switzerland.

March 2024
Publication of:
ACTION PLAN SUPPORTING COARA 2024

EQUALITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION

Amid growing global challenges to equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI), Science Europe launched the Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments in February 2024.

Developed by the Task Force on EDI, the guide offers actionable recommendations to foster inclusive research cultures across Europe, reinforcing Science Europe's commitment to embedding these values in research policies and practices.

As we face an increasingly complex global landscape, where the values of equality, diversity, and inclusion are at risk, Science Europe is resolutely committed to ensuring that these principles continue to be prioritised in research policies and practices. On 1 February, Science Europe launched its Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments.

The guide, developed by the Task Force on EDI, highlights findings from a 2023 membership survey and offers practical recommendations on topics like positive action measures and the collection and use of diversity data, building on the 2017 Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations.

The guide reflects on the challenges faced by research organisations in fostering inclusive cultures and provides recommendations to support diversity in national research systems. It is part of Science Europe's broader commitment to embedding shared values in policies and practices that support high-quality, fair, and attractive research environments across Europe.

A launch event, introduced by the current and former Science Europe Presidents Mari Sundli Tveit and Marc Schiltz, included perspectives on diversity and highlighted areas of progress and those requiring further action. Science Europe is committed to continuing efforts to improve diversity in research.

+ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-culture/equality-diversity-inclusion/>

“Ensuring equality, diversity, and inclusion in research is not just a goal, but a continuous commitment. With the launch of this guide, Science Europe reinforces its dedication to fostering inclusive research environments that are essential for high-quality, impactful science across Europe.”

ANNA DI CIACCIO / DIRECTOR OF THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR NUCLEAR PHYSICS (INFN), ITALY.

2024 WOMEN IN SCIENCE CAMPAIGN

Each year, to mark the International Day for Women and Girls in Science and International Women's Day, Science Europe organises a campaign to celebrate and promote gender equality in research and innovation.

The 2024 Women in Science Campaign, which ran between 11 February and 8 March, showcased good practices from Science Europe Member Organisations in support of gender equality. It also featured short video interviews with several members of the Science Europe Governing Board, who shared insights on institutional efforts, personal experiences to promote gender equality, and the importance of inclusive research environments.

▶ [2024 Women in Science \(YouTube\)](#)

RESEARCH INTEGRITY & ETHICS

In 2024, Science Europe re-emphasised research integrity as a key pillar of healthy and effective research cultures.

Through the publication of its Statement on Research Integrity, it highlighted the roles of funding and performing organisations in maintaining ethical standards. Building on strategic collaborations, workshops, and international engagement, Science Europe continues to champion integrity in research policies and practices across Europe.

As one of the six shared values in its Values Framework, Science Europe brought research integrity to the forefront in 2024 through a range of policy initiatives, international engagement, and strategic collaborations. At the heart of these efforts was the development and publication of its new Statement 'Integrity at the Heart of Healthy and Effective Research Cultures' in July. The statement, created by the Task Force on Research Integrity, outlines the roles and responsibilities of research funding and performing organisations in upholding integrity and offers actionable recommendations to support responsible research practices.

A major milestone in this work was the first-time participation in the World Conference on Research Integrity, held in Athens in June 2024. Science Europe presented an advanced draft of the statement and collected feedback from the international community. The final version links research integrity to attractive working environments, open science, and research assessment reform, reaffirming the vital role of integrity in ensuring research quality and public trust in science.

Science Europe also took an active role in shaping future policy by co-proposing a new Action on integrity for the 2025–27 ERA Policy Agenda, in collaboration with the European Commission's DG RTD. It also explored opportunities for international collaboration with the European Network of Research Integrity Offices and contributed to several Horizon Europe initiatives, including [IRISE](#), [OSIRIS](#), and [TIER2](#), which address reproducibility and responsible research practices.

In addition to these policy-level contributions, Science Europe engaged directly with the research community through targeted workshops. These included a symposium with QUEST – the Centre for Responsible Research at the Berlin Institute of Health on research rigour, and a workshop on reproducibility led by the TIER2 project. Both events emphasised the need to embed research integrity and trust as core elements of research quality and offered practical tools and recommendations for institutions and funders.

Looking ahead, the Science Europe Task Force on Research Integrity and the Working Group on Research Culture will continue to advance this agenda. They will support collaborative approaches across the European Research Area, such as platforms for knowledge exchange, and the development of shared operational tools to navigate the evolving challenges of modern research, including the use of emerging technologies such as AI.

“Research integrity remains the foundation of robust, trustworthy, and impactful research. Through strategic leadership and strong partnerships, Science Europe is helping shape a research culture in which integrity is not just upheld, but championed.”

FRANCISCO JAVIER MORENO FUENTES / VICE-PRESIDENT FOR INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS, SPANISH NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (CSIC)

July 2024

Publication of Position Statement: **INTEGRITY AT THE HEART OF HEALTHY AND EFFECTIVE RESEARCH CULTURES**

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-culture/integrity-ethics/>

OPEN SCIENCE

In 2024, Science Europe continued to strengthen open science and scholarly communication systems building on the momentum of the [2023 European Council Conclusions](#). It focused on policy development, community engagement, and sustainable infrastructure.

Key efforts included identifying synergies between open science and research assessment and promoting Diamond Open Access as a sustainable model. Through collaborations with members and international partnerships, Science Europe advanced open science initiatives across Europe and globally.

A key activity was the effort to establish a robust evidence base for open science strategies and their integration into research assessment practices. Discussions during dedicated meetings of the Working Groups on Open Science and Research Culture focused on mutual learning, policy alignment, and capacity building. At a joint meeting in September, the results from the comprehensive membership survey 'Strategic Approaches to, and Research Assessment of, Open Science' shaped key discussions on strategic approaches, monitoring, and evidence gathering.

The results of the survey were presented during International Open Access (OA) Week in October and attracted strong interest from the research community. The findings will inform future work on developing recommendations to support open science implementation across research funding and performing organisations.

Important steps were taken to reinforce Diamond OA as a sustainable, equitable model for scholarly publishing. The association engaged with its Member Organisations to discuss their participation in [Open Research Europe](#), leading to a joint Statement of Intent to manage the initiative collectively from 2026 onwards.

It was signed by eleven members in early 2025. Science Europe co-organised two webinars for endorsers of the Action Plan for Diamond OA,

as well as the [2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) in Cape Town, South Africa. The Summit focused on social justice in scholarly communication, culminating in the Toluca-Cape Town Declaration and reinforcing global collaboration with partners from Africa, Latin America, and Europe.

Other milestones in the development of a co-ordinated global ecosystem for Diamond OA were the [announcement event](#) and consultation for the Global Diamond OA Framework, both organised by UNESCO. These are further strengthened by the public launch of the [European Diamond Capacity Hub](#) and the EU-funded [ALMASI](#) project in January 2025.

Science Europe contributed to international policy debates, responding to the UNESCO Draft Principles of Open Science Monitoring and welcoming the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#). These initiatives reflect our commitment to transparency and the importance of openly shared, comparable research information across systems. The development of institutional policy recommendations was also supported through participation in the Horizon Europe [DIAMAS](#) project. A co-design workshop in April brought together funders and donors to explore how best to support the Diamond OA ecosystem, with results published in May 2025.

Recognising the evolving components of open science, the publication of recommendations for 'Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software' offered practical advice to embed software into broader open science strategies. In parallel, Science Europe also took part in the [PRO-MaP](#) project to promote reusable and open research methods.

“As we reflect on a year of strong engagement and forward-looking initiatives, Science Europe remains committed to working with its European and global partners to ensure open science becomes embedded across the research ecosystem. In 2025, we will deepen our efforts through workshops, policy development, and international collaboration - continuing to shape a more open, inclusive, and effective research landscape.”

ANU NOORMA / DIRECTOR GENERAL OF THE ESTONIAN RESEARCH COUNCIL (ETAG)

8-14 December 2024
Organisation of event:
2nd GLOBAL SUMMIT ON DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS
Cape Town, South Africa.

September 2024
Publication of
Survey Report:
**STRATEGIC APPROACHES
TO AND RESEARCH
ASSESSMENT OF
OPEN SCIENCE**

September 2024
Publication of
Recommendations:
**DEVELOPING AND
ALIGNING POLICIES
ON RESEARCH
SOFTWARE**

+ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/>

SHAPE EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Acting as a strong voice for sustainable and responsible policies in the European Research Area.

Work with the European Commission to co-develop a proposal for an ERA Action on a harmonised European framework for integrity and ethics.

Advocating for a strong European R&I Research Framework Programme.

Championing Equitable Global Partnerships and Inclusion in International Research.

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

Through active engagement in shaping the European Research Area, influencing the next EU Framework Programme, and promoting equitable international collaboration, Science Europe worked to ensure that research remains a cornerstone of Europe's competitiveness, inclusivity, and sustainability.

This year's milestones reflect the organisation's strategic commitment to advancing a values-based research ecosystem – one grounded in academic freedom, scientific excellence, and global co-operation.

In 2024, Science Europe continued its active engagement in shaping the ERA by advancing strategic priorities and contributing to key policy developments, ensuring that its members' voices are reflected in policy processes and advocating shared research values and goals. A major milestone was the publication of a briefing on the ERA Policy Agenda 2022–24. This document, spanning ten ERA Policy Actions such as research assessment reform, research careers, integrity and ethics, open science, and science communication, outlines Science Europe's actions, advocacy positions, and messages in relation to the ERA priorities. These materials were developed in close collaboration with Science Europe's Working Groups, Governing Board, and General Assembly, and underpin its engagement on European research policy.

Discussions also continued during 2024 on the actions to be included in the ERA Policy Agenda 2025–27, many of which align with Science Europe's strategic priorities. These include key areas such as international collaboration, equality and inclusion, greening research, and the responsible use of artificial intelligence. In May 2025, the EU Council adopted the ERA Policy Agenda 2025–27, which includes a proposal for a harmonised European framework on integrity and ethics, one of two submissions put forward by Science Europe. In addition to policy development, Science Europe actively participated in key ERA-related events. The ERA Conference in September marked four years of the renewed ERA, featuring high-level panels and breakout sessions on topics such as academic freedom, science communication, AI, and reforming research assessment. It also contributed to a major milestone in research culture: the launch of the ERA Forum sub-group's Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct on Gender-Based Violence and Sexual Harassment in the EU Research and Innovation System, reaffirming the EU's commitment to creating safe and equitable research environments.

“The European Research Area must be built on a foundation of shared values – academic freedom, research integrity, and inclusivity. In 2024, Science Europe strengthened its role as a trusted voice in shaping this vision by championing policies that promote responsible research practices and sustainable collaboration. Together with our members, we remain committed to advancing a research ecosystem that builds on excellence, is open, ethical, and equipped to meet Europe's future challenges.”

KATARINA BJELKE / DIRECTOR GENERAL OF THE SWEDISH RESEARCH COUNCIL (VR)

April 2024
Publication of Briefing Paper:
**THE ERA POLICY AGENDA
2022-2024**

+ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/cross-border-collaboration/high-level-policy-network/>

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

(Continued)

As the European Parliament adopted a resolution that called on the European Commission to promote academic freedom across the EU in January, Science Europe continued to advocate on this issue. Its 'Vote for Science' campaign in May urged candidates in the June European Parliament elections to commit to supporting science-informed policy making, based on freedom of scientific enquiry, and values of collaboration, openness, and equity.

Following the elections, Science Europe engaged with newly elected MEPs to position itself as a key interlocutor on research and innovation policy, particularly in the context of the next Framework Programme.

In January, Science Europe and the Research Council of Norway (RCN) hosted a workshop addressing the complexities of compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in international collaborations. While progress has been made in developing tools and policies, challenges remain in ensuring clarity and consistency when working with partners outside the European Economic Area. Feedback was also provided to the European Commission through the call for evidence for the 2025 GDPR report.

In May, Science Europe also submitted its initial response to the European Commission's White Paper on dual-use research. It called for a flexible, risk-based approach and highlighted the need to distinguish civil from defence research, protect basic research funding, and maintain international openness. These priorities will continue to guide Science Europe's engagement in shaping FP10 and future EU research policy.

In addition, Science Europe has continued to be active in the implementation of the Directive on the Protection of Animals Used for Scientific Purposes. In coordination with its Member Organisations, it participates in the meetings of the National Contact Points for the Directive.

"In 2024, Science Europe championed the importance of research autonomy and clarity in critical areas like GDPR and dual-use research. By ensuring that Europe's research ecosystem remains open, accountable, and internationally connected, we aim to nurture an environment where research and innovation can thrive for the greater good."

MARCEL LEVI / PRESIDENT OF THE DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

Science Europe Feedback on the Implementation of the GDPR

Brussels, February 2024

Introduction

Science Europe welcomes the opportunity to provide feedback on the implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the context of international collaborations. The 2025 GDPR report, Science Europe supports the major European public research funding and performing organisations, together spending over €50 billion per year on research in cross-border, multi-national and multi-institutional settings. These organisations are crucial to the success of the European research ecosystem. It is therefore essential to ensure that the GDPR is implemented in a way that respects the values of openness, equity, and collaboration that underpin the European research ecosystem.

Key findings and recommendations

Science Europe's research organisations have identified several key findings and recommendations regarding the implementation of the GDPR in international collaborations. These include the need for greater clarity and consistency in the interpretation of the regulation, the importance of maintaining international openness and equity, and the need to ensure that the GDPR does not create unnecessary barriers to international research. Science Europe is committed to working with the European Commission and other stakeholders to address these challenges and ensure that the GDPR is implemented in a way that respects the values of the European research ecosystem.

Key recommendations

- Clarify the interpretation of the regulation in the context of international collaborations.
- Ensure that the GDPR does not create unnecessary barriers to international research.
- Maintain international openness and equity in the implementation of the regulation.
- Ensure that the GDPR respects the values of the European research ecosystem.

Next steps

Science Europe will continue to work with the European Commission and other stakeholders to address the challenges identified in this report. We will also continue to engage with our member organisations to ensure that their voices are heard in the development of the 2025 GDPR report.

More Clarification and Discussion Needed

Science Europe initial response to the European Commission public consultation on its White Paper on Dual-Use Research

Science Europe welcomes the release of the European Commission's initial response to the public consultation on its White Paper on Dual-Use Research. We are pleased to see that the Commission has taken account of the views of researchers and researchers' organisations in its response. However, we believe that more clarification and discussion is needed on several key issues. In particular, we are concerned about the Commission's proposed approach to the regulation of dual-use research. We believe that a more flexible, risk-based approach is needed, one that distinguishes between civil and defence research. We also believe that the Commission's proposed approach to the regulation of basic research funding is insufficient. We believe that more support is needed for basic research, and that the Commission should ensure that international openness and equity are maintained in the implementation of the regulation. Science Europe is committed to working with the Commission and other stakeholders to address these concerns and ensure that the regulation is implemented in a way that respects the values of the European research ecosystem.

Key findings and recommendations

- A more flexible, risk-based approach is needed to regulate dual-use research.
- The Commission should ensure that international openness and equity are maintained in the implementation of the regulation.
- More support is needed for basic research, and the Commission should ensure that international openness and equity are maintained in the implementation of the regulation.

Next steps

Science Europe will continue to work with the Commission and other stakeholders to address the concerns identified in this report. We will also continue to engage with our member organisations to ensure that their voices are heard in the development of the White Paper.

January 2024
Publication of:
SCIENCE EUROPE FEEDBACK ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GDPR

May 2024
Publication of:
SCIENCE EUROPE RESPONSE TO THE EU WHITE PAPER ON DUAL-RESEARCH

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation/>

EU FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES: HORIZON EUROPE AND FP10

As Europe prepares for its next EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Science Europe has been at the forefront of shaping its future direction.

In 2024, the organisation amplified its advocacy for a bold and inclusive 10th Framework Programme (FP10), outlining clear priorities to ensure research remains central to Europe's competitiveness, resilience, and societal wellbeing.

As the current programme, Horizon Europe, draws to a close in 2027, Science Europe intensified its advocacy for an ambitious and inclusive successor. '10 Key Messages for FP10', published in July 2024, called for increased investment in research and innovation, while protecting academic freedom, promoting open science and responsible international collaboration, and fostering diversity and inclusion. It also presented proposals to strengthen science communication and accessibility, and called for renewed investment in peace research.

These messages were also the basis for the 'Vote for Science' campaign to raise awareness of the essential role science plays in addressing societal challenges, ahead of the 2024 European Parliament elections. Launched during the 'Vote for Science' workshop in May, it called on candidates to commit to five core pledges – focusing on increased investment, academic freedom, collaboration, equality, and the vital role of science communication.

In parallel, Science Europe joined the broader Research Matters campaign, a pan-European initiative that unites universities, research organisations, funding agencies, industry, and communications professionals. The campaign calls for increased R&D investment – at least 3% of GDP in all European countries – and advocates a doubled and ring-fenced budget for the next Framework Programme.

Science Europe was one of the signatories of the campaign's open letter to EU policy makers, published on 4 June, and co-organised a public event in Brussels in October on the campaign themes with key interventions from former Italian Prime Minister Enrico Letta, MEP Christian Ehler, and Maria Leptin, President of the European Research Council.

Throughout the year, Science Europe continued to closely monitor discussions around FP10 and the upcoming Multiannual Financial Framework (2028–34), which is expected to be unveiled in mid-2025.

Drawing from the outcomes of the 'Vote for Science' workshop and in-depth engagement with its Member Organisations, Science Europe also published 'What European Research Needs' in November. This document responded directly to high-level reports by Enrico Letta, Mario Draghi, and Manuel Heitor, reiterating the case for an ambitious and well-funded EU research programme.

Among the key recommendations were maintaining support for existing instruments like the European Research Council and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, ensuring balance between low- and high-TRL research, reducing administrative burdens, and enhancing capacities for research across the continent. The paper also reinforced the importance of ensuring that EU research programmes remain open to international participation.

During 2024, in collaboration with the Working Group on Horizon Europe's Task Force on R&I integration, Science Europe Members from 'widening' countries took part in a series of interviews, based on the six key points in the position statement 'Science Europe Recommendations to Reduce Research and Innovation Disparities and Foster Brain Circulation'. In the spirit of moving from 'widening' to 'R&I integration' (bridging the R&I gap in Europe), these interviews built on the recommendations with data and good practices, and have been incorporated in our advocacy strategy towards FP10.

Looking ahead to 2025, Science Europe will continue to advocate a strong, well-funded, and inclusive research and innovation ecosystem – one that positions science as a fundamental pillar of Europe's competitiveness and resilience.

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-framework-programmes/>

"As we look towards the next Framework Programme, it is essential that we invest in research and innovation that not only drives Europe's competitiveness but also upholds the values of academic freedom, collaboration, and inclusivity. Science Europe is committed to advocating for a research ecosystem that is open, sustainable, and capable of addressing the societal challenges of today and tomorrow."

MARI SUNDLI TVEIT /
CHIEF EXECUTIVE OF THE RESEARCH COUNCIL OF NORWAY (RCN)

October 2024
Campaign launch:
RESEARCH MATTERS

May 2024
Campaign launch:
VOTE FOR SCIENCE

CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

In 2024, Science Europe strengthened its efforts to shape international research collaboration around the principles of equity, reciprocity, and shared responsibility. It championed inclusive and trust-based approaches to global partnerships that reflects diverse perspectives and common goals.

During the year, Science Europe deepened its commitment to fostering more equitable and reciprocal international research collaborations, particularly with partners across Africa. Through a series of strategic engagements, the organisation championed a shift from 'science for society' to 'science with society', underscoring the importance of inclusivity, trust, and mutual benefit in global scientific partnerships.

Science Europe welcomed the Africa–Europe Science and Innovation Platform (AERAP) to a roundtable during the 4th AERAP Africa–Europe Science Collaboration Forum. The discussion highlighted the critical need for inclusive international co-operation and the importance of co-design in research partnerships. Participants raised concerns about underrepresentation of African leadership in global agendas such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and stressed the importance of involving all stakeholders in shaping regulations – especially in areas like artificial intelligence and data governance.

Visa restrictions, ambiguity in regulations, and asymmetries in capacity were recognised as ongoing barriers to collaboration. To counter these, there was strong support for more inclusive policy making and the integration of African perspectives into EU research initiatives, including the design of the upcoming Framework Programme. Ensuring that FP10 reflects a truly global partnership, and not a Eurocentric agenda, was a key takeaway.

These themes continued to be explored at the event 'Reciprocity in Multilateral Research Collaboration', co-organised with the Research Council of Norway (RCN) at the Science Summit during the 79th UN General Assembly in New York in September.

Building on the outcomes of the 2023 High Level Workshop on international research collaboration, speakers from across the globe discussed how trust and inclusion must underpin partnerships, noting that multilateral collaboration must move "at the speed of trust." Open Science was highlighted as a foundational element to ensure equitable access to knowledge and uphold academic freedom.

Furthering this work, Science Europe, in partnership with its members RCN, ETAG, DFG, NWO, and UKRI, hosted a dialogue on Africa–Europe collaboration following the GRC European Regional Meeting in Tallinn in October, as part of a new workshop series to explore regional partnerships one world region at a time. The inaugural workshop with African partner organisations highlighted both the persistent challenges – such as visa issues, capacity imbalances, and Eurocentric agendas – and promising opportunities for strengthening more balanced and sustainable collaborations.

16TH HIGH LEVEL WORKSHOP ON THE ERA

Strengthening European cohesion and competitiveness through research and innovation.

The 16th edition of the High Level Workshop on the European Research Area was held on 19–20 November 2024 in Budapest, co-organised by Science Europe, the Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN), and the Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA). Taking place under the auspices of the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU, the workshop brought together heads of national research organisations, EU policy makers, and academics to explore how research and innovation can drive cohesion and competitiveness across Europe.

The 2024 edition focused on widening participation in European R&I, enhancing impact through EU-wide scientific excellence, reducing disparities, and exploring the role of artificial intelligence in science policy. As well as presenting the results of interviews with Member Organisations to assess current integration efforts and identify persistent structural obstacles, the event was also an opportunity to reaffirm the importance of scientific freedom, institutional autonomy, and open dialogue as key values in the development of a more integrated, globally competitive European R&I ecosystem.

Science Europe and its co-organisers published a [Concluding Statement on Commitment to Strengthening European R&I](#), outlining six shared priorities: ensuring academic freedom, safeguarding institutional autonomy, improving researcher mobility, increasing R&I funding to 3% of GDP, fostering fair international collaboration, and advancing Open science practices.

Participants stressed that competitiveness must go hand in hand with inclusivity. To achieve this, research systems across Europe must eliminate structural barriers, reduce administrative burdens, and improve working conditions for researchers. Integrating AI responsibly and aligning national strategies with European objectives were also identified as essential steps forward.

The 2024 workshop reinforced the value of the ERA as a platform for high-level dialogue and action. The outcomes of this event will guide future efforts by Science Europe to build a more cohesive, competitive, and collaborative research environment across Europe.

[▶ Watch the event video](#) [+](#) [Read the event report](#)

"In 2024, Science Europe reinforced its commitment to building international research partnerships grounded in trust, inclusivity, and reciprocity. We believe that the future of science hinges on collaboration that transcends traditional divides, integrating diverse voices and perspectives to ensure research benefits us all."

FRANCISCO JAVIER MORENO FUENTES /
VICE-PRESIDENT FOR INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS, SPANISH NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (CSIC)

17 September
Organisation of event:
RECIPROCITY IN MULTILATERAL RESEARCH COLLABORATION
New York, US.

30 October
Organisation of event:
COOPERATION BETWEEN AFRICA AND EUROPE - BEST PRACTICE, FUTURE POSSIBILITIES AND THE ROLE OF SCIENCE EUROPE
Tallinn, Estonia.

19-20 November
Organisation of event:
16TH HIGH-LEVEL WORKSHOP ON THE ERA
Budapest, Hungary.

CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

(Continued)

COLLABORATION WITH THE NATIONAL NATURAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION OF CHINA

In 2024, Science Europe continued to explore avenues of co-operation with Chinese research institutions, in particular with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC).

A webinar on 10–11 April and an in-person high-level meeting in Beijing on 11–12 October discussed the topics of research talent development and data sharing. Participants agreed that data sharing is important for the promotion of knowledge, international collaboration, and excellence. Among the key messages from the meeting in Beijing was that information about collaboration is as important as collaboration itself, and that international research co-operation in addressing global challenges should be built on trust and reciprocity. The meeting concluded with an agreement to continue collaboration, with plans for an NSFC delegation to visit Brussels in 2025. Future discussions will focus on the role of research funding organisations in global challenges, open science, and research assessment.

GLOBAL RESEARCH COUNCIL

The 2024 Annual Meeting of the Global Research Council (GRC), hosted by the Science Europe member Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the Côte d'Ivoire Fund for Science, Technology, and Innovation (FONSTI) focused on the themes of sustainable research, research for sustainable development, and ways to enhance the sustainability of research practices. The discussions resulted in the adoption

of a [Statement of Principles](#) that reaffirmed the GRC's commitment to promote all forms of research that: support sustainable development and address global environmental, social, and economic challenges; incentivise responsible research practices; and, work towards the systemic changes and participatory approaches needed to make sustainability science matter.

Science Europe co-organised a side-event on equality, diversity and inclusion as part of its contribution to the discussions, as well as the European Regional Meeting. Marcel Levi, Science Europe Vice-President and President of the Dutch Research Council (NWO), and Katja Becker, President of the German Research Foundation (DFG), were elected to the GRC Governing Board, joining Science Europe President Mari Sundli Tveit in a new chapter for the Council's leadership.

The GRC European Regional Meeting took place on 28–31 October in Tallinn, Estonia. Co-organised with the Estonian Research Council (ETAG), discussions focused on two topics: 'Research Management in the Era of AI' and 'Working Together in Co-Creation to Address Global Challenges'. The conclusion was that while AI integration boosts efficiency, it should remain a supportive tool and not replace human judgement. Effective co-creation should begin with a thorough understanding of the problem, through a "co-design" phase where all stakeholders collaboratively define the core issue.

The main outputs of the discussions from all Regional Meetings were synthesised into a [Statement of Principles](#) that was endorsed during the 2025 GRC Annual Meeting in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

28-31 October 2024
Organisation of event:
GRC EUROPEAN REGIONAL MEETING
Tallinn, Estonia.

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/cross-border-collaboration/>

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

In 2024, Science Europe continued to shape global conversations on research infrastructure by deepening its collaboration with the OECD and engaging in high-level discussions on sustainable, inclusive, and strategically aligned research infrastructure (RI) systems.

Through expert groups, workshops, and international conferences, the organisation worked to ensure the international RI landscape is supported and equipped to meet evolving scientific and societal needs.

In 2024, Science Europe strengthened its long-standing collaboration with the OECD Global Science Forum (OECD-GSF), contributing to a new Expert Group on RI ecosystems. This group aims to explore practical models for integrated RI systems and held a workshop in February, examining governance, partnerships, and access.

Science Europe also contributed to a workshop co-organised by OECD-GSF and the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures on assessing public investments in RIs. Governing Board member Milica Đurić-Jovičić emphasised the need for robust financial data to better understand and justify RI funding across their full life cycles, highlighting the importance of aligning RI financing with broader research policy objectives at both national and international levels.

This issue was also discussed at the 2024 International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI) in Brisbane. The conference explored global themes such as digital infrastructures, sustainability, and the inclusion of indigenous knowledge.

The concluding [Brisbane Statement](#) echoed many of Science Europe's priorities, calling for more strategic governance, stronger collaboration, and increased investment in RIs to address shared global challenges.

“In today’s interconnected world, the future of research infrastructures lies in building stronger, more inclusive international partnerships. Science Europe is committed to fostering collaboration that transcends borders, ensuring that research infrastructures are a shared global asset, supporting ground-breaking fundamental research, addressing grand societal challenges, and driving innovation for the benefit of all.”

MILICA ĐURIĆ-JOVIČIĆ / ACTING DIRECTOR OF THE SCIENCE FUND OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA (SFRS)

STRENGTHEN THE ROLE AND CONTRIBUTION OF SCIENCE IN TACKLING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Promoting science-informed decision making to support policy makers in tackling societal issues and advancing sustainable development.

Exploring the potential and challenges posed by AI tools in science.

Developing a roadmap to build connections between researchers and society, including organisation for a high-level conference on science communication.

GREENING RESEARCH

In 2024, Science Europe deepened its commitment to sustainability by advancing key initiatives to reduce the environmental impact of research. A major milestone was the publication of a new Framework to guide Member Organisations in embedding sustainability into research and research-related practices.

Through strategic partnerships, data-driven insights, and global engagement – including COP29 – Science Europe contributed to strengthening the role of research in climate action.

As global awareness of the climate crisis grows, so does the responsibility of research organisations to lead by example and play their part in tackling climate change. In 2024, Science Europe significantly advanced its strategic commitment to environmental sustainability in research through a series of high-impact initiatives, strategic collaborations, and new policy outputs.

Following the 2024 mid-term strategy review and growing focus on Artificial Intelligence through a dedicated Task Force, the Working Group on the Green and Digital Transition became the Working Group on Greening Research, underscoring the strengthened focus on sustainability. Building on previous efforts, the Working Group consolidated 'Greening Research' as a central pillar of Science Europe's activities to embed sustainability into research policies, funding strategies, and operational practices.

In November, Science Europe published the Framework for the Environmental Sustainability of Research Organisations, a landmark strategy document developed by the Working Group that sets the goal of promoting environmental sustainability on the systemic level in Europe, contributing to the objectives of the European Green Deal and international environmental governance. It outlines a long-term vision and sets eight thematic action areas to guide Member Organisations in making their research and research-related activities more environmentally sustainable. A webinar series on greening research, held in May and June in partnership

with ANR, AKA, DFG, FCT, FORMAS, INFN, NWO, SNSF, and UKRI, raised awareness on the environmental impacts of research activities, discussed solutions for reducing the environmental footprint of research organisations, and provided examples of good practices from Member Organisations, laying the groundwork for the publication of the Framework.

Complementing the Framework, the survey report Appraising Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Research Organisations was released in December. It provided a baseline for understanding how Science Europe members assess and act on their carbon footprints. Two-thirds of the 22 responding organisations had conducted an appraisal of their greenhouse gas emissions, and nearly 80% were already implementing or developing strategies for emission reduction. This data will inform forthcoming guidelines on carbon accounting and mitigation.

As part of efforts to strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges, Science Europe was formally granted observer status to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and participated in COP29 in Baku, Azerbaijan. President Mari Sundli Tveit, alongside representatives from the Office and Working Group, engaged in bilateral meetings and contributed to high-level side events on science-policy co-operation and climate action, bringing Science Europe perspectives into the global discussions on climate change.

2025 will see continued implementation of the Framework, the development of shared guidelines for emissions reduction, and the development of a European Network on Greening Research Practices. Science Europe will also contribute to policy consultations and preparations for COP30 in Belém, Brazil.

“Research organisations have an important role to play in addressing the climate crisis – not only through the knowledge they generate, but in how they operate. With our new Framework and continued collaboration across Europe and beyond, Science Europe is taking concrete steps to embed sustainability at the heart of the research system.”

MARCEL LEVI / PRESIDENT OF THE DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

December 2024
Event participation:
**SCIENCE EUROPE PRESIDENT
MARI SUNDLI TVEIT SPEAKS AT COP29**
Baku, Azerbaijan.

December 2024
Publication of Survey Report:
**APPRAISING GREENHOUSE
GAS EMISSIONS OF
RESEARCH
ORGANISATIONS**

July 2024
Publication of Report:
**GREENING
RESEARCH
WEBINARS SERIES
FINAL REPORT**

+ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/greening-research/>

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

In 2024, Science Europe strengthened its focus on embedding science communication in research and innovation. Through high-level events and strategic collaborations, the organisation emphasised the need for science communication to be a core element of research culture and policy.

Key initiatives included a major conference on science communication in policy making, new guidance for science-for-policy activities, and discussions on the role of AI in science communication, all aimed at fostering transparency, trust, and evidence-based decision making.

Science Europe, in collaboration with the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO) and the Fund for Scientific Research (FNRS), co-organise the high-level conference 'Unlocking the Power of Science Communication in Policy Making' in March, under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union. This landmark event brought together more than 480 participants and 66 expert speakers from research, policy, media, and civil society. Discussions focused on the vital role of science communication in addressing societal challenges, enhancing trust in science, and advocating sustained investment in research.

The event emphasised the need to integrate communication strategically from the outset of research programmes to ensure transparency, public engagement, and improved scientific literacy. This approach was presented not only as a means of making science more accessible and transparent, but also as a powerful tool for highlighting the societal value of public investment in research. A recurring theme was the need to move beyond ad hoc outreach and instead make science communication a sustained, strategic component of research funding and practice.

Following the conference, the outcomes were captured in [Strategic Conclusions](#) and a comprehensive [final report](#). These publications outlined several key recommendations for national and European policy makers, research organisations, and funding agencies. They called for science communication to be incentivised and rewarded within research environments, the recognition of science communication as a distinct professional field, and the promotion of AI literacy and data transparency in science communication. They also stressed the importance of upholding principles of integrity, inclusivity, and accountability to foster public trust in science.

In April, Science Europe launched its 'Guidance on Science for Policy Activities' at a public event hosted by FWO. It was designed to support research organisations in strengthening their engagement with policy makers, ultimately contributing to more effective, evidence-informed decision making. It highlights the need for a long-term, well-resourced approach to science-for-policy activities, underpinned by institutional mandates, transparent processes, and strong relationships between the research and policy communities.

Another milestone during 2024 was a webinar on artificial intelligence in science communication for Science Europe members. This online discussion explored the opportunities and ethical challenges AI technologies present, including issues around responsible integration, data bias, and the development of practical guidelines for AI use, stressing the importance of human oversight.

As Science Europe looks ahead to 2025, its Working Group on Communication will build on this year's achievements. Planned activities include the publication of new guidance for members on integrating science communication into research processes and the organisation of a conference on public trust in science, in partnership with the French National Research Agency (ANR), to take place in December.

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/science-communication/>

"Science communication is much more than a tool; it is essential for building trust, fostering transparency, and ensuring that research serves society's needs. As we look ahead, Science Europe is committed to making science communication a strategic and sustained part of research culture and policy."

CHRISTOPHER SMITH / EXECUTIVE CHAIR OF THE ARTS AND HUMANITIES RESEARCH COUNCIL, UK RESEARCH INNOVATION (UKRI)

March 2024
Organisation of event:
UNLOCKING THE POWER OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION
Brussels, Belgium.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In 2024, Science Europe focused on supporting its members in navigating the rapid advancement of the use and implications of Artificial Intelligence in research.

Through its Task Force on AI and a series of webinars, the organisation explored AI's impact on research evaluation, management, and science communication, while ensuring core values like ethics and transparency are maintained.

With the rapid evolution of generative AI and machine learning, Science Europe's initiatives focused on understanding the opportunities, challenges, and implications of these technologies for research evaluation, management, communication, and how their benefits can be balanced with preservation of core research values, including ethics, transparency, reliability, and reproducibility.

Reflecting the growing importance of AI in research, Science Europe launched a Task Force on AI, comprising representatives from each of its Working Groups to explore shared priorities, assess key trends, challenges, and opportunities in different research contexts. The results of a membership survey, published in April, informed the development of a programme of activities to support their needs. This included the organisation of three webinars during the year, focusing on the use of AI in research evaluation, the legal aspects of implementing AI in research organisations, and the use of AI for science communication.

Members provided feedback to the European Commission on their 'Living Guidelines for the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research', while an internal discussion paper published at the end of the year set out areas for further consideration, such as the role of AI in application and evaluation processes, taking account the environmental impacts of AI in research, and the research infrastructure needed to support the continued growth of AI technology.

As part of efforts to promote and advance dialogue with other relevant policy stakeholders and research communities, Science Europe joined the CoARA Working Group on Ethics and Research Integrity Policy in Responsible Research Assessment for Data and Artificial Intelligence (ERIP). The group will develop good practice recommendations and tools to foster and ethical and responsible culture for the assessment of data and AI in research, fostering responsibility, transparency, and societal benefit.

"As AI continues to reshape the research landscape, Science Europe is committed to helping its members navigate these changes responsibly and build a shared understanding of how AI can be integrated into research systems in ways that enhance quality, uphold ethical standards, and align with broader societal values."

CHRISTOF GATTRINGER / PRESIDENT OF THE AUSTRIAN SCIENCE FUND (FWF)

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation/artificial-intelligence/>

AFTERWORD

As we close another impactful year, I am filled with deep appreciation for the dedication, insight, and collaboration that have shaped Science Europe's work throughout 2024. This report reflects not only the breadth of our activities, but also the strength of the community that makes them possible. An interesting holistic approach is generated by integrating the outcomes of the different activities of the association.

In a year marked by complex challenges and rapid developments – from the evolving role of artificial intelligence to the imperative of environmental sustainability and the emergence of research security as a priority for international collaboration, Science Europe has continued to lead and support its Member Organisations in shaping policies, practices, and partnerships that reflect shared values and long-term ambition. Together, we addressed vital topics ranging from research assessment and environmental sustainability to AI, science communication, and international collaboration, with clarity, courage, and purpose.

Many of our achievements during 2024 were only possible through the collective expertise and commitment of our Member Organisations and the expert representatives who contribute so actively to our Working Groups, Task Forces, and strategic dialogues. I am profoundly grateful for their time, their trust, and their belief in our mission. I would also like to express my heartfelt thanks to the staff of the Science Europe Office, whose professionalism and drive are behind every initiative detailed in this report.

We look forward to analysing the proposals for the next Multi-Annual Financial Framework and the Tenth EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10). We will continue to advocate the key values and factors that the extensive knowledge and experience of our

Member Organisations have as national public research funding and research performing organisations. These honour the principle that science is a public good, as the reader can clearly see through the activities and outcomes presented in the 2024 Annual Report.

Together, also in collaboration with the stakeholder organisations in ERA, we are shaping a European research environment that, in addition to upholding the highest standards of scientific excellence, the values of openness, collaboration, and responsibility. Against this evolving landscape, our mission remains clear: to advance research systems that are open, responsible, sustainable, and grounded in shared values. I look forward to continuing to deepen our collaboration: the future of research depends on what we build together.

“2024 has shown the power of collective action grounded in shared values. I am deeply grateful to our Member Organisations and dedicated staff whose commitment has made this year’s achievements possible.

As we navigate complex challenges, our unity and vision continue to shape a research environment that is open, responsible, and fit for the future. The strength of our community gives me great confidence.”

LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN
SECRETARY GENERAL SCIENCE EUROPE

ANNEX

WORKING GROUP ON OPEN SCIENCE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Armesto, Lourdes	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Ball, Sara (from Aug)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Barać Lauc, Lovorka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Bianco, Stefano (from June)	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Bilic-Merdes, Michaela	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Bojo Canales, Cristina (until Dec)	Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Bolliger, Isabel	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Bruce, Rachel	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Carić, Dejana	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Chorošenin, Petr	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Clarke, Patricia (from Apr)	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Cruz, Maria (chair)	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Dular, Mirjam (from Feb)	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Galica, Natalia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Garnier, Martine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Garrido, Julián	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Glotov, Sergiy	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Halling, Sanja	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Hammarberg, Tove	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Hautala, Harri	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Irimia, Alina	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Jeney, Silvia (from Nov)	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Kita, Jean-Claude	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Kokorevičs, Arnis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Kutnyánszky, Anikó	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Kuznetsov, Andriy	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Larsen, Tore Burkal (from May)	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Meeus, Joke	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Mertens, Jan	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Mirlina, Liga	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Montesanti, Annalisa	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Nordin, Lissa	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Novais, Joana	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Pazik-Aybar, Aneta	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Philipp, Tobias	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Piirsoo, Marko	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Podolieva, Alina	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Ponsati, Agnes	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Pristovšek, Primož (until Aug)	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Qvenild, Marte (until Dec)	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Robotka, Balázs	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Rosendahl, Lasse Aistrup	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Wojtyra, Wiktorja	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland

CHAIR:

Maria Cruz

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Bregt Saenen

TASK FORCE ON OPEN RESEARCH SOFTWARE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Cruz, Maria	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Karcher, Stefan	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Katerbow, Matthias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Martinez Ortiz, Carlos	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Perez, Daniel	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Popa, Andreea	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Bregt Saenen

WORKING GROUP ON RESEARCH CULTURE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Adriani, Oscar <i>(from June)</i>	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Baltzrud, Lillian M.	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Barać Lauc, Lovorka <i>(Sep-Dec)</i>	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Bolliger, Isabel	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Boyarsko-Khomenko, Anna <i>(from Apr)</i>	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Cañibano, Carolina <i>(until May)</i>	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Carić, Dejana <i>(from September)</i>	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Cody, Anne	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Dypvik, Trude	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Gayoso, Pilar	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Grimm, Tobias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Guyard, Laurence	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Györfi, Miklós	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Holm, Jon	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Jarecka-Stępień, Katarzyna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Juurik, Marten	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Kokorevičs, Arnis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Kolotilov, Sergey <i>(until April)</i>	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Lachat, Fanny	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Łazarowicz-Kowalik, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Martinović Klarić, Irena <i>(until Jul)</i>	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Mik-Meyer, Nanna <i>(until May)</i>	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Milovanović Soldatić, Sandra <i>(until Sept)</i>	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Molíková, Eva	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Montoliu, Lluís	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Nordin, Lissa	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Ochsenfeld-Repp, Sonia	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
O'Leary, Jo	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Olsson, Emma	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Penders, Stefan <i>(from September)</i>	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Sánchez, Irene	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Sapcariu, Sean <i>(co-chair)</i>	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Schiøtt, Birgit <i>(until May)</i>	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Ségérie, Audrey	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Sigurðsson, Sigurður Óli	Icelandic Centre for Research (Rannís)	Iceland
Šinkūnienė, Jolanta <i>(co-chair)</i>	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Söderlind, Johan	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Steinczinger, Zsuzsanna <i>(until May)</i>	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Stevanovic, Ana	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Strinzel, Michaela	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Tienen, Ingrid van	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Valosaari, Kata-Riina	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Vranešević, Goran	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia

CO-CHAIRS

Sean Sapcariu, Jolanta Šinkūnienė

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

James Morris

TASK FORCE ON EQUALITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Isala, Ana	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Jonsson, Inger	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Lorenzini, Jasmine	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Mik-Meyer, Nanna	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
O'Leary, Jo	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Reichwein, Eva	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Thijs, Tim	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Wampach, Linda	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Westholm, Lisa	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

James Morris

TASK FORCE ON OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH ASSESMENT MEMBERSHIP SURVEY

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Clarke, Patricia	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Halling, Sanja	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Irimia, Alina	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Györfi, Miklós	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Mertens, Jan	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Jeney, Sylvia	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Zaidi, Tahia	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Bregt Saenen, James Morris

TASK FORCE ON RESEARCH INTEGRITY

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Boland, Marion	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Kolu, Päivi	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Lachat, Fanny	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Montoliu, Lluís	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ottinger, Teresa	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Rouby, Asael	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Steinberger, Martin	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Veitch, Rebecca	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

James Morris

TASK FORCE ON RESEARCH CAREERS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Baltzrud, Lillian	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Buckow, Anjana	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Olsson, Emma	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Sapcariu, Sean	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Schiøtt, Birgit	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Ségerie, Audrey	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Valosaari, Kata-Riina	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Van Acker, Frederik	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

James Morris

WORKING GROUP ON HORIZON EUROPE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancāns, Jānis	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Bak, Sebastiaan den <i>(until Jun)</i>	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Brookes, Jonathan	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Bühler, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Devine, Ellenor	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Drury, Georgina	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Fängström, Britta	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Forster, Fabienne	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Herranz Cecilia, Aida	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Kazai, Zsolt <i>(until May)</i>	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Kostka, Sylwia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kotarba, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Malvezzi, Sandra <i>(from June)</i>	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Marjanen, Katja	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Miller, Christina	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Møller, Tom-Espen	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Mortensen, Maria <i>(until May)</i>	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Nakath, Richard	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Nash, Maria	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Nissilä, Rami	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Oitmaa, Kristel	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Rebhan, Christian	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Rodríguez, Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Serrano, Joaquín	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Szendrey, Adrienn	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Szepesvári, Krisztina <i>(Chair)</i>	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Taranov, Igor <i>(from Apr)</i>	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Torrent, Moira <i>(from Oct)</i>	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Totland, Karin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Van Hauwaert, Ann	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Wel, Esther van der <i>(from Dec)</i>	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Wittorski, Natacha	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Zagalo Pereira, Gonçalo <i>(from Feb–until Sep)</i>	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal

CHAIR:

Krisztina Szepesvári

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Sophie Lemahieu, Adrien Bream, Márton Kottmayer

WORKING GROUP ON COMMUNICATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Aksjonova, Darja	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Allik, Anneli	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Ármansson, Davíð Fjölur	Icelandic Centre for Research (Rannís)	Iceland
Barbé, Kim	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Bastong, Benedikt	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Bilyi, Oleksandr	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Blomberg, Elisabet	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Bóné, Péter Pál	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Chorošenin, Petr	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Delvax, Liesbeth	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Evensen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Ferreira, Joana	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Fleetwood, Anna Maria	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Futrell, Jane (<i>until Oct</i>)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
García Gonzalo, Marta	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ginic, Natalija	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Goossens, Didier	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Grau, Abel	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Harket, Hilde Totland	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hoekstra, Ynte	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Houssein, Sherylee	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Imperiali, Fabrice	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Janů, Vojtěch	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Korzekwa-Józefowicz, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kranewitter, Stefan	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Le Floch, Katel	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Lečić, Dario	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Machulina, Tetiana	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Markey, Gillian	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Nill, Christian	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
O'Driscoll, Lorna	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Ólafsson, Alda	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ortega, Inés	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Plaza, Jose Antonio	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Prats, Jaime (<i>from Dec</i>)	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Rotar, Adriana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Sarbach, Jun	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Thuveesson, Zandra	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Tuetey, Stéphanie	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Varaschin, Antonella	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Winnen, Eric	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium

CHAIR:

Anneli Allik

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Rosemary Hindle

TASK FORCE ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY	WG MEMBER
Ait Ameer, Yamine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France	Greening Research
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy	Open Science
Evensen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Communication
Gyorffi, Miklos	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary	Research Culture
Hasgall, Alexander	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland	High-Level Policy Network
Holm, Jon	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Research Culture
Marjanen, Katja	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland	Horizon Europe
Oitmaa, Kristel <i>(since July)</i>	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia	Horizon Europe
Ochsenfeld-Repp, Sonja	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany	Research Culture
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary	Greening Research
Webb, Sarah	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom	Greening Research

CHAIR:

Lidia Borrell-Damián

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Theodora Famprikezi, Adrien Braem

TASK FORCE ON R&I INTEGRATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achterberg, Jörn	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Adojaan, Maarja	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Ancāns, Jānis	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Bóhm, Gergely	Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA)	Hungary
Bühler, Sarah	Swiss National Research Foundation (SNSF)	Swiss
Chioncel, Mariana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Đurić-Jovičić, Milica <i>(until June)</i>	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Gębalska, Malwina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Grossi, Ludovica	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
István, Szabó	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Kotarba, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Łazarowicz, Marta	Polish Foundation for Science (FNP)	Poland
Mekinda Vidmar, Blanka	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Mydlo, Stanislav	Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV)	Slovakia
Pětrašová, Kamila	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Polašek, Ozren	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Povilaiškė, Aurelija	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Szepesvári, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary

CHAIR:

Krisztina Szepesvári

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Theodora Famprikezi, Sophie Lemahieu

HIGH-LEVEL POLICY NETWORK

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Absillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Adriani, Oscar <i>(from Jun)</i>	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Bak, Sebastiaan den <i>(until Jun)</i>	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Bärenreuter, Christoph	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Bell, Linda	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Berndt, Anja	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Boc, Mojca	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Bonenkamp, Berry <i>(from Jul)</i>	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Burg, Helena	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Chioncel, Mariana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Curaj, Adrian	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Danielsen, Kristin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Domínguez, Elena	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Dunon-Bluteau, Dominique	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Đurić-Jovičić, Milica <i>(until Jul)</i>	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Fängström, Britta	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Folea, Antoaneta	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Groeneveld, Joël	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Hakala, Johanna	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hasgall, Alexander	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Lindholm, Maria	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Maguire, Teresa	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Markussen, Lisbet Crone <i>(from May)</i>	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Marti, Simon <i>(until July)</i>	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Martinović Klarić, Irena <i>(until Jul)</i>	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Mekinda Vidmar, Blanka <i>(from June)</i>	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Mico Egea, Victoria <i>(until Jul)</i>	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Mistrík, Robert	Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV)	Slovakia
Muižniece, Lauma	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Nieto Garcia, Maria Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Noorma, Anu	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Ognois, Laure	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Oppenrieder, Elias <i>(from Mar-Jul)</i>	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Pětrašová, Kamila	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Poll, Myriam	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Rebhan, Christian	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Reding, Laurin	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Sara-Kennedy, Rachael	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Schmidt, Finn <i>(from Dec)</i>	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Serritzlew, Søren <i>(from May)</i>	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Słomińska, Kinga	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Sümeghy, Gyula	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Törnqvist, Stefan	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Verbaeys, Isabelle	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wentker, Sibylle <i>(from Feb)</i>	Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW)	Austria
Wiley, Paul	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Woźniakowska, Justyna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Zagalo Pereira, Gonçalo <i>(until Sep)</i>	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Zondaka, Elita	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia

CHAIR HLPN ON CBC: Helena Burg
CHAIR HLPN ON ERA: Lidia Borrell-Damián

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Adrien Braem (ERA), **Sophie Lemahieu** (CBC), **Theodora Famprikezi**

TASK FORCE ON MONITORING CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Absillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Lečić, Dario	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Burg, Helena	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Butt, Dominique	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Lee, Natasha	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Telford, Myriam	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Muppavarapu, Vydehi	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Łazarowicz Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Martínez, Catalina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Martin-Lanuza, Monica	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Neouze, Maïa	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Repnik, Robert	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Strzebońska, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Učakar Petrovčič, Lucija	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Virlon, Bérangère	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Vodjdani, Nakita	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Wojciechowska, Paulina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Sophie Lemahieu, Theodora Famprikezi

TASK FORCE ON CHINA

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Bain, Magnus	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Bak, Sebastiaan den	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Bonenkamp, Berry	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Durrans, Sophie	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Krüßmann, Ingrid	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Schlepper, Gerrit Andreas	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wiley, Paul	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Sophie Lemahieu, Theodora Famprikezi

WORKING GROUP ON GREENING RESEARCH

(Working Group on the Green & Digital Transition until May 2024)

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achermann, Sarah (until Aug)	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Aït-Ameur, Yamine (Co-chair)	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Beaufort, Anne Marie de	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Broquard, Sophie (from Dec)	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Clarke, Patricia	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Dalla Vecchia, Marta (from Feb)	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Daly, Amanda (from May)	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Danielsen, Kristin (until Mar)	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Del Río González, Pablo	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Diaz, Julio	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Farley, Martin (from Dec)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Ferre, Marian	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Heylen, Steven	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Imrik, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Jarecka-Stepień, Katarzyna (until Feb)	National Science Center (NCN)	Poland
Joerk, Christiane	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Kaell, Christiane	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Kamerer, Tamara (from Mar)	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Karamik, Sule (from Mar)	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Kjeldby, Brage (from Dec)	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Klobučar, Marko (until Dec)	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Lamba, Sakshi (from Aug)	Research Ireland (RI)	Ireland
Łazarowicz-Kowalik, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Leskinen, Paula	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Malme, Tarjei Nødtvedt (Mar-Dec)	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Matt, Ina (from Feb)	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
McGrath, Emma (from Feb)	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Mobjörk, Malin (until Feb)	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Polašek, Ozren (from Dec)	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Prado, Margarida (co-chair)	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Prieur-Richard, Anne-Hélène	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Quilitz, Lea (from Aug)	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Ryan, Michael (until Dec)	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Thoonen, Guy (until Dec)	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Webb, Sarah	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

CO-CHAIRS:

Yamine Aït Ameur, Margarida Prado

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Nicola Francesco Dotti (until June), **Diana Potjomkina**

TASK FORCE ON ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF DIGITALISATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achermann, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Aït-Ameur, Yamine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Beaufort, Anne Marie de	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Del Río González, Pablo	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Prado, Margarida	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Diana Potjomkina

TASK FORCE ON GREENING RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achermann, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Del Río González, Pablo	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Imrik, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Heylen, Steven	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Kaell, Christiane	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
O'Brien, Shona	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Prieur-Richard, Anne-Hélène	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Stuefer, Josef	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Thoonen, Guy	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Winkler, Amelie	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Diana Potjomkina

TASK FORCE ON GUIDANCE FOR SCIENCE-POLICY INTERFACES

(Activities ended April 2024)

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Aït-Ameur, Yamine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Clarke, Patricia	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Mobjörk, Malin	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Prado, Margarida	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Stuefer, Josef	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Webb, Sarah	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Nicola Francesco Dotti

SCIENCE EUROPE STAFF MEMBERS 2024

NAME	TITLE
Lidia Borrell-Damián	Secretary General <i>Since September 2019</i>
Adrien Braem	Senior Policy Officer <i>Since October 2017</i>
Sara Cesari	Policy Officer <i>Until March 2025</i>
Nicola Francesco Dotti	Senior Policy Officer <i>Until June 2024</i>
Riccardo Durante	Administrative Assistant <i>Until April 2024</i>
Stéphanie Flouquet	Personal and Administrative Assistant <i>Since March 2021</i>
Rosemary Hindle	Communications Manager <i>Since February 2024</i>
Iwan Groeneveld	Communications and Events Officer <i>Since June 2015</i>
Alexander Halksworth	Communications Officer <i>Since September 2023</i>
Márton Kottmayer	Policy Officer <i>Since October 2024</i>
Sophie Lemahieu	Senior Policy Officer <i>Until February 2025</i>

NAME	TITLE
James Morris	Senior Policy Officer <i>Since July 2019</i>
Diana Potjomkina	Senior Policy Officer <i>Since September 2024</i>
Artemis Rodopoulou	Office Manager <i>Since August 2013</i>
Bregt Saenen	Senior Policy Officer <i>Since November 2021</i>
Claire Salinas	Senior Policy Officer <i>Until May 2024</i>

SCIENCE EUROPE PUBLICATIONS 2024

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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ERA, HORIZON EUROPE AND FP10

Joint Statement on Investing More in RD&I as a Strategic Move for Europe's future Prosperity	January
Report of the 2023 High Level Workshop on the ERA	March
Briefing on the ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024	April
Vote for Science 5 Pledges	May
Joint Letter on A call to strengthen research and innovation in Europe	June
10 Key Messages for the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10)	July
Science Europe Response to the European Commission Consultation on the New ERA: Four Years On	September
Joint Statement on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	October
What European Research Needs	November
Concluding Statement on Commitment to Strengthening European R&I	December
Report of the 2024 High Level Workshop on the ERA	December

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

Conclusions from 'Reciprocity in Multilateral Research Collaboration' event	October
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RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Science Europe CoARA Action Plan	April
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RESEARCH CAREERS

Attractive Careers in Research: the Expectations & Roles of Different Stakeholder Groups	December
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RESEARCH INTEGRITY

Integrity at the Heart of Healthy and Effective Research Cultures	July
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OPEN SCIENCE

2nd Diamond Open Access Conference Report	February
Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software: Recommendations for RFOs and RPOs	September
Report of the Science Europe survey: 'Strategic approaches to, and research assessment and monitoring of open science'	October
Support for UNESCO Draft Principles on Open Science Monitoring	November

SCIENCE EUROPE PUBLICATIONS 2024 (CONTINUED)

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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EU LEGISLATION

Open Letter to the European Commission not to Neglect the Needs of European Research and Higher Education Organisations in Lawmaking	January
Science Europe Feedback on the implementation of the GDPR	February
Initial Position in response to European Commission's Public Consultation on the White Paper on R&D on Dual-Use Technologies	May

GREENING RESEARCH

Greening Research Webinars Series: Final Report	July
Framework for the Environmental Sustainability of Research Organisations	November
Survey Report: Appraising Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Research Organisations	December

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Science Communication Conference Strategic Conclusions	March
Guidance on Science for Policy Activities	April
Science Communication Conference report	July

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Member Survey on the Uses of Artificial Intelligence in Research Processes: Analysis of Outcomes and Ways Forward <i>(Members only)</i>	April
Science Europe Webinar On AI: Trends In Implementing AI In Research Organisations & Legal Aspects <i>(Members only)</i>	July
Internal Discussion Paper on 'Artificial Intelligence' <i>(Members only)</i>	December

OTHER

Updated Multi-annual Action Plan	June
From Ambition To Action: Fostering Research Excellence In Europe - 2023 Annual Report	July

SCIENCE EUROPE MAIN EVENTS 2024

TITLE	EVENT DATE
Launch of the Science Europe Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments - <i>Brussels, Belgium</i>	1 February
CoARA National Chapters Forum - <i>Porto, Portugal</i>	22–23 February
Unlocking the Power of Science Communication in Policy Making - <i>Brussels, Belgium</i>	12–13 March
Launch of Science–Policy Guidelines - <i>Brussels, Belgium</i>	4 April
Voting for Science: The Role of Science in Europe - <i>Brussels, Belgium</i>	14 May
Series of Webinars on Greening Research - <i>online</i>	21, 28 May, 4 June
Reciprocity in Multilateral Research Co-operation - <i>New York, US</i>	16–17 September
GRC European Regional Meeting - <i>Tallinn, Estonia</i>	28–31 October
Co-operation between Africa and Europe – best practice, future possibilities, and the role of Science Europe - <i>Tallinn, Estonia</i>	30 October
Workshop on Attractive Careers in Research: the expectations & roles of different stakeholder groups - <i>Brussels, Belgium</i>	4–5 November
Rethinking Research Assessment - <i>Bucharest, Romania</i>	14 November
High Level Workshop on the European Research Area: Strengthening European Cohesion and Competitiveness through Research and Innovation - <i>Budapest, Hungary</i>	19–20 November
2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access - <i>Cape Town, South Africa</i>	1–7 December

Colophon

2024 SCIENCE EUROPE ANNUAL REPORT:
ADVANCING EXCELLENCE, REALISING IMPACT

Month: July 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15791143

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Science Europe AISBL

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